

Notice: Logsheet

Each time a sampling is carried out one has to fill in a logsheet. This has to be done with care because all the information requested is needed during the analysis of the samples and the data evaluation process.

General information

Anything written on the logsheets will be interpreted by a text recognition algorithm. Manual validation will be necessary, but please follow the following best practices:

- Use a dark pen to write on the logsheets, preferably black or dark blue
- Write in **English**
- Write with **detached** letters, no handwriting with connected letters
- Write with **capital** letters as much as possible
- Write **inside the text boxes**; anything outside will not be annotated
- When you **tick a box**, put a fat **dot** rather than a cross or a check mark

Always write information inside the dedicated square, never out.

For any comment and precision use the dedicated space **COMMENTS**. There are never too many details !

You can find 2 different logsheet, one for the sampling at sea, one for the sampling on shore. Please use the correct one.

Step-by-step instruction

GENERAL INFORMATION

SHIP ID: write the MMSI number of your vessel, corresponding to 9 numbers.

LEG: write the LEG number of your mission.

INVESTIGATOR: write the name and surname of the sampler (e.g., SMITH MORGAN).

STATION: write the number of the station, use number and no name of station.

DATE: write the sampling date respecting the format YEAR/MONTH/DAY (e.g., 2024/11/13). Be careful to use the correct format.

SEA STATE: write the sea state number of the station using the Beaufort scale (see appendix).

PRECIPITATION: Four precipitation state, No precipitation, light rain, moderate rain and heavy rain.

CLOUD COVERAGE: Five cloud coverage model are represented on the logsheet. Please add a dot under the most representative pourcentage coverage model at the moment of your sampling.

SAMPLING PART

CAST: A cast correspond to a deployment. Several nets can be deployed. Basically one cast = one net

NET MODEL: Choose the net model between the 4 categories: MystiNet, CLASSIC, HSN and DIODON. If you use on other model, please fill the “other” section.

TOW TYPE: Add a dot in the good tow type

MESH SIZE: Add a dot on the corresponding mesh size: 20 or 50 μ m. If you choose another mesh size, please write the number in the “other” section.

DEPLOYMENT: write the different parameters of the deployment: rope angle in degree (angle between the cable and the water), depth minimum and depth maximum in meter, and cable out (cable deployed in the water) in meter.

LAT/LONG: write the latitude and longitude at the beginning of the cast and at the end following the model “North/South, Decimal Degree”, MM.MMM” for latitude and “E/W, DD”, MM.MMM”

UTC TIME: write the start and end time of your net tow. Be careful to use the UTC time

DAY or NIGHT: Indicate whether sampling takes place during the day or at night

ADDITIONAL INFOS (if measure is possible)

TOW SPEED: This value is for vertical net, indicate the ascent speed in knots.

AIR T°: Write air temperature in degrees Celsius.

SEA WATER T°: Write sea water temperature in degrees Celsius.

WIND SPEED: Write wind speed in knots.

WIND DIRECTION: Write wind direction in degrees.

WAVE DIRECTION: Write wave direction in degrees.

CTD: Indicate the name of the model and cable out in meters.

FLOWMETER: Indicate the name of the model and the value before and after the sampling specify unit.

SECCHI DISC: Write the depth when the disc is no longer visible.

FILTRATION TREATMENT (Lamprey)

FINAL VOLUME AFTER NET RINSING: Measure the volume contained in the cod-end

POROSITY: write the porosity number of the filter used

START/END TIME UTC: write the start and end time of your filtration. Be careful to use the UTC time

BARCODE: Stick on the dedicated space the barcode sticker, the little one on the logsheet, the bigger one on the tube.

TUBE ID: If you don't have barcode stickers, add a tube ID.

FILTERED VOLUME: Write the volume filtered through the filter.

SATURATION: If the filtration is very low and only few drops come out of the pipe you have reached filter saturation.

If you had a **duplicate** (from the same sampling), fill the "filter n°2" part

IMAGING TREATMENT (Planktoscope)

FINAL VOLUME AFTER NET RINSING: Measure the volume contained in the cod-end.

PROJECT NAME: Name of the project you indicate in the Sample tab before the acquisition in the Planktoscope.

STATION ID: ID based on Station and Cast number, this is the same ID you fill in Sample tab.

DILUTION (/CONCENTRATION): If you make a dilution or a concentration of your sample to make the acquisition.

Acq ID to import: ID number corresponding to your acquisition.

Nb of images: Number of images you make for this acquisition.

Nb of Objects: Number of objects you obtain after segmentation of your acquisition data.

APPENDIX 1 – Beaufort Scale

Estimating Wind Speed and Sea State with Visual Clues

Beaufort number	Wind Description	Wind Speed	Wave Height	Visual Clues
0	Calm	0 knots	0 feet	Sea is like a mirror. Smoke rises vertically.
1	Light Air	1-3 kts	< 1/2	Ripples with the appearance of scales are formed, but without foam crests. Smoke drifts from funnel.
2	Light breeze	4-6 kts	1/2 ft (max 1)	Small wavelets, still short but more pronounced, crests have glassy appearance and do not break. Wind felt on face. Smoke rises at about 80 degrees.
3	Gentle Breeze	7-10 kts	2 ft (max 3)	Large wavelets, crests begin to break. Foam of glassy appearance. Perhaps scattered white horses (white caps). Wind extends light flag and pennants. Smoke rises at about 70 deg.
4	Moderate Breeze	11-16 kts	3 ft (max 5)	Small waves, becoming longer. Fairly frequent white horses (white caps). Wind raises dust and loose paper on deck. Smoke rises at about 50 deg. No noticeable sound in the rigging. Slack halyards curve and sway. Heavy flag flaps limply.
5	Fresh Breeze	17-21kts	6 ft (max 8)	Moderate waves, taking more pronounced long form. Many white horses (white caps) are formed (chance of some spray). Wind felt strongly on face. Smoke rises at about 30 deg. Slack halyards whip while bending continuously to leeward. Taut halyards maintain slightly bent position. Low whistle in the rigging. Heavy flag doesn't extended but flaps over entire length.
6	Strong Breeze	22-27 kts	9 ft (max 12)	Large waves begin to form. White foam crests are more extensive everywhere (probably some spray). Wind stings face in temperatures below 35 deg F (2C). Slight effort in maintaining balance against wind. Smoke rises at about 15 deg. Both slack and taut halyards whip slightly in bent position. Low moaning, rather than whistle, in the rigging. Heavy flag extends and flaps more vigorously.
7	Near Gale	28-33 kts	13 ft (max 19)	Sea heaps up and white foam from breaking waves begins to be blown in streaks along the direction of wind. Necessary to lean slightly into the wind to maintain balance. Smoke rises at about 5 to 10 deg. Higher pitched moaning and whistling heard from rigging. Halyards still whip slightly. Heavy flag extends fully and flaps only at the end. Oilskins and loose clothing inflate and pull against the body.
8	Gale	34-40 kts	18 ft (max 25)	Moderately high waves of greater length. Edges of crests begin to break into the spindrift. The foam is blown in well-marked streaks along the direction of the wind. Head pushed back by the force of the wind if allowed to relax. Oilskins and loose clothing inflate and pull strongly. Halyards rigidly bent. Loud whistle from rigging. Heavy flag straight out and whipping.
9	Strong Gale	41-47 kts	23 ft (max 32)	High waves. Dense streaks of foam along direction of wind. Crests of waves begin to topple, tumble and roll over. Spray may affect visibility.
10	Storm	48-55 kts	29 ft (max 41)	Very high waves with long overhanging crests. The resulting foam, in great patches is blown in dense streaks along the direction of the wind. On the whole, the sea takes on a whitish appearance. Tumbling of the sea becomes heavy and shock-like. Visibility affected.
11	Violent Storm	56-63 kts	37 ft (max 52)	Exceptionally high waves (small and medium-sized ships might be for time lost to view behind the waves). The sea is completely covered with long white patches of foam lying along the direction of the wind. Everywhere, the edges of the wave crests are blown into froth. Visibility greatly affected.
12	Hurricane	64+ kts	45+ ft	The air is filled with foam and spray. The sea is completely white with driving spray. Visibility is seriously affected.